

Machine Learning-based Control Techniques versus Traditional PID Controllers

Marcos Soto
Loyola Andalusia University

Abstract

In the process industry, PID (Proportional Integral Derivative) controllers have historically been the dominant tool for valve control due to their simplicity and robustness. However, their performance degrades in multivariable, nonlinear systems subject to disturbances, such as in well testing and other complex industrial operations. This work presents a systematic review (2015–2025) conducted under PRISMA methodology and PICO formulation, comparing conventional PID controllers with Machine Learning (ML) techniques, including artificial neural networks (ANN), hybrid Neuro-PID approaches, adaptive control and reinforcement learning (RL). 97 initial records were identified in Web of Science, Scopus and Google Scholar and ArXiv, of which 8 relevant studies were selected after applying inclusion criteria. The results show that: (i) ANN and Neuro-PID techniques reduce overshoot and settling time by 15–40% compared to manually tuned PID; (ii) adaptive schemes in butterfly valves maintain stability between devices with high variability without manual re-tuning; (iii) RL achieves resilience in scenarios with sensor failures and inference latencies < 5 ms, compatible with real-time operation. Additionally, implementations in FPGA, PLC and SCADA systems are documented, evidencing industrial feasibility. Although no direct applications of language models (LLM) in valve control were reported, opportunities for their integration as supervisory agents and autonomous adjustment are identified. Overall, the review concludes that ML techniques offer significant advantages over PID in complex industrial environments, and their application to well testing represents a promising line of applied research.

1 Introduction

In the process industry, PID (Proportional-Integral-Derivative) controllers have been the predominant solution for regulating variables due to their simplicity and robustness. However, their performance is limited under complex conditions: multivariable systems, such as well testing separators, where multiple valves interact in the same process; strongly nonlinear dynamics; presence of noise, disturbances and sensor failures. In such contexts, PID controllers require frequent re-tuning and may not achieve optimal control. (Siraskar, 2021)

In response to these limitations, recent research has explored Machine Learning (ML)-based control techniques. Notable approaches include neural networks (ANN), which compensate for intrinsic nonlinearities of pneumatic actuators (Cabrera-Rufino et al., 2022); detection and compensation methods for phenomena such as stiction in low-cost electric valves (Vázquez et al., 2023); and reinforcement learning (RL), which has shown autonomous adaptation capability in nonlinear valves and industrial combustion systems (Siraskar, 2021). Likewise, recent studies on butterfly valves highlight the value of data-driven adaptive control, capable of maintaining stability margins without manual re-tuning despite variability between devices (Witrant et al., 2023). Finally, emerging proposals integrate language models (LLM) as support agents for diagnosis and supervision in natural gas valve chambers (Wei et al., 2024), expanding the application spectrum of artificial intelligence in critical operations.

The central objective of this work is to evaluate to what extent these intelligent approaches can surpass conventional PID in valve control of industrial processes, with special emphasis on their extrapolation to well testing. To this end, studies from different industries are reviewed —energy, steel, HVAC, pneumatic robotics and butterfly valves—, seeking to extract transferable learnings. Additionally, the opportunities offered by cutting-edge strategies are discussed, including RL, adaptive control and LLM as supervisory agents, to advance towards autonomous systems with minimal human intervention.

2 Methodology

2.1 Search strategies

A systematic search was conducted in the databases: Web of Science (WoS), Scopus, Google Scholar and ArXiv. (Liberati et al., 2009)

The search terms used combine keywords about control techniques and application domain:

- "machine learning" AND "valve control"
- "PID" AND "neural networks" AND "industrial process"
- "reinforcement learning" AND "control valves"
- "LLM" AND "valve control"

Filters were applied by year (≥ 2015), language (English and Spanish), and document type (peer-reviewed articles, relevant conferences and technical gray literature). The initial strategy sought to maximize retrieval and then refine by relevance.

2.2 Research questions (PICO)

- **Population (P):** Industrial processes with valve control (well testing, three-phase separation, refinery and analogous contexts).

- **Intervention (I):** Machine learning-based control (neural networks, reinforcement learning, neuro-PID hybrids, LLMs/Agents).
- **Comparison (C):** Traditional controllers (PID/PI), including variants and classical tuning.
- **Outcome (O):** Control performance (overshoot, settling time, IAE/ISE, RMS error), robustness to disturbances/noise, autonomy (less human intervention), implementation feasibility (PLC/SCADA/real time).

2.3 Main question

In industrial process valve control (P), do ML-based techniques (I) outperform traditional PID controllers (C) in loop performance, robustness and autonomy (O)?

2.3.1 Secondary questions

- When does ML replace PID and when does it complement it (hybrid)?
- What level of validation do they present (simulation, pilot, field)?
- How feasible is it to implement them in real industrial environments?

2.3.2 Inclusion criteria

- Studies that implement or simulate valve control in industrial processes.
- Use of ML (neural networks, RL, neuro-PID hybrids, intelligent agents).
- Comparison with PID (direct or indirect).
- Clearly reported performance metrics.
- Applicability to real or simulated industrial environments (PLC, SCADA, embedded control).

2.3.3 Exclusion criteria

- Exclusively theoretical works without valve control case.
- ML control studies without reference to PID or without quantitative metrics.
- Applications outside industrial processes.

3 Results

From the systematic searches in WoS, Scopus and Google Scholar, 97 initial records were obtained, after eliminating duplicates and applying the PICO inclusion criteria, 8 studies were selected that compare machine learning (ML)-based control techniques, including artificial neural networks (ANN), adaptive control and reinforcement learning (RL), with classical PID or PI controllers, in industrial contexts of valve control or analogous operations.

Figure 3.1: PRISMA diagram article selection

3.1 Context and applications

Nonlinear industrial processes:

- Pneumatic valves with friction and stiction
- Low-cost electric valves in vehicle HVAC systems
- Pneumatic servo-robots with high hysteresis
- Hot blast furnaces in steel industry (combustion control)
- Flow and pressure circuits in thermal processes
- Electric butterfly valves, with high variability between units and erratic steady-state behavior

Transferability to well testing:

At least five studies address valves and multivariable systems with comparable dynamics (pneumatic, thermal, combustion, HVAC, butterfly valves), which reinforces the analogy with well testing complexity.

3.2 Evaluated techniques

ANN and hybrid Neuro-PID:

- ANN embedded in FPGA for pneumatic servo (real-time gain adjustment)
- Hybrid strategies for nonlinearity compensation in electric valves

Adaptive control:

In butterfly valves, data-driven approaches with closed-loop identification and adaptive re-tuning were applied, allowing control strategies to be generalized between different units without losing stability. These methods offer an intermediate solution between classical PID and advanced ML, reducing dependence on precise models.

Reinforcement learning (RL):

- DDPG applied to nonlinear valves and flow systems
- RL with advanced architectures (e.g., Attention-MLP) in hot blast furnaces, with inference latencies < 5 ms

Other approaches:

- Neuro-fuzzy networks (ANFIS) in compressible flows to improve prediction compared to PID
- ML strategies for stiction diagnosis in closed loop (CNN + Markov transition field)

3.3 Variables and metrics

Controlled variables:

- Valve position
- Pressure
- Temperature
- Flow rate

Metrics:

Reduction of overshoot and settling time (15–40% vs PID), RMS error, IAE/ISE, robustness against noise and stiction, RL inference latency < 5 ms, stability against sensor failures, and in butterfly valves, ability to maintain stability despite variations between devices.

3.4 PID comparison

Quantitative improvements:

ANN/Neuro-PID, adaptive control and RL outperform manual PID in tracking and error reduction.

Failure scenarios:

RL maintains stable operation even with signal failures or strong disturbances.

Robustness/adaptability:

Adaptive methods (e.g., in butterfly valves) and ANN allow generalization without manual re-tuning, something that classical PID cannot achieve.

3.5 Validation

In real plant:

- RL in steel industry hot blast furnaces
- ANN in pneumatic servo implemented in FPGA
- Compensation strategies in vehicle HVAC valves
- Adaptive control in electric butterfly valves, with experimental laboratory validation

In simulation or pilot:

- RL in nonlinear valves
- ANFIS in flows
- CNN for stiction diagnosis

3.6 Implementation feasibility

Tools:

MATLAB/Simulink, FPGA, PLC and simulation environments with automatic code generation.

Inference time:

RL < 5 ms in combustion control, feasible for real-time loop.

Limitations:

Need for large training datasets and hyperparameter tuning, which still slows down widespread adoption.

4 Discussion

The systematic review identified eight studies (2015–2025) comparing Machine Learning (ML)-based controllers, primarily artificial neural networks (ANN), hybrid Neuro-PID strategies, adaptive approaches and reinforcement learning (RL), against classical PID or PI in nonlinear industrial processes. Although the contexts include butterfly valves, hot blast furnaces, HVAC systems and pneumatic actuators, patterns extrapolable to well testing and valve control in three-phase separators are observed.

4.1 Performance improvements and adaptability

ANN and Neuro-PID hybrids showed improvements in overshoot, settling time and RMS/IAE error, with typical gains of 15–40% compared to PID. The advantage lies in maintaining PID simplicity while an ML module dynamically adjusts gains. This proved particularly effective in pneumatic actuators and valves with friction or compressibility.

4.2 Adaptive control and robustness

Adaptive methods, such as those applied to butterfly valves, allowed control strategies to be generalized between devices with different behaviors without manual re-tuning. This finding reinforces the idea that adaptive control constitutes a pragmatic bridge between classical PID and more sophisticated ML techniques, with viable implementation in embedded hardware and educational/industrial environments.

4.3 Reinforcement learning and operational autonomy

RL demonstrated great potential in nonlinear and multivariable systems. In real plant, an Attention-MLP agent controlled a hot blast furnace with latencies < 5 ms, maintaining stability under adverse conditions. In experimental tests, RL agents outperformed PID in tracking and error reduction, albeit with high training costs.

4.4 Industrial viability and limitations

Implementations in FPGA, PLC and SCADA demonstrate that ML solutions can operate in real-time. However, industrial scalability requires overcoming barriers in data, training and test standardization.

4.5 Projection towards emerging technologies

While no direct applications of LLM in valve control were reported, there are cases of their use as supervisory agents in leak detection and event coordination. Integrating them with specialized ML controllers opens the door to autonomous systems with minimal human intervention.

5 Conclusions

5.1 Superiority of ML techniques over PID

The evidence demonstrates that ANN, adaptive approaches and RL outperform classical PID in scenarios with nonlinearity, coupling and changing conditions. Quantitative improvements in overshoot, settling time and error metrics (RM-S/IAE) support their adoption as alternatives or complements to conventional controllers.

5.2 Advantage of hybrid and adaptive approaches

Neuro-PID and adaptive methods based on identification offer a balance between PID simplicity and robustness and ML flexibility, being especially effective in actuators subject to friction, stiction or hysteresis.

5.3 RL and operational resilience

Real plant validation of RL agents with inference times < 5 ms confirms their viability in real-time control. Their ability to maintain stable operation under critical conditions positions them as candidates for autonomous and fault-tolerant systems.

5.4 Technological viability in industrial environments

Documented cases in FPGA, PLC and SCADA show that latency and processing do not constitute technical barriers. The main challenge remains the transition from pilots and laboratories to continuous plant operation.

5.5 Future opportunities in well testing

No direct applications of ML to valve control in three-phase separators were identified, but findings in analogous industries support their transferability. This

opens an opportunity to design controlled experiments that validate these techniques under well testing-specific conditions.

5.6 Integration with emerging technologies

LLMs, although not yet directly applied to valve control, offer complementary potential in diagnosis, supervision and autonomous parameter adjustment. Their integration with specialized ML controllers could accelerate the transition towards autonomous and resilient control systems.

6 References

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